

Gut Analysis of *RITA. rita* (Hamilton, 1822) From Fish Market of Quetta City, Balochistan Pakistan

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Abstract

Rita rita is commonly known as rita and belong to the family bagridae. This fish is widely spread Afghanistan, Bangladesh, India, Myanmar, Nepal and Pakistan. Samples of fish were taken between January and December 2022 at the Quetta local fish market. About 260 fish samples were dissected to determine the gut analysis. Volumetric and Frequency occurrence method was used to determine the gut analysis. The gut fullness and gastronomic index were also calculated. All the guts noted the seasonal variations. There were around of 41 (14.28%) stomachs were empty, 63 (23.21%) were three quarter, 46 (16.07%) were full, and half guts were 62 (28.59%). The gut fullness on a monthly basis in month of January 80%, February (75%), March (72%), April (70%), June (60%), July (65%), August (70%), September (79%), October (87%), November (88%) and December (85%) respectively. Gastronomic symptoms peaked in the months of October and December, while June had the lowest levels. During the current study following gut contents were recorded such as Fishes 25.22% and 26.31%, Phytoplankton 14.21% and 12.22%, Zooplankton 11.10% and 13.50%, Crustacean 9.33% and 11.26%, Insects 8.41% and 10.29%, Plecoptera 6.88% and 8.11%, Hemiptera 7.12% and 6.22%, Coleoptera 5.24% and 5.22%, Mud and Sand 5.33% and 4.19%, Miscellaneous 2.99% and 1.24%, Leaves 2.38% and 1.12%, Aquatic weeds 1.02% and 0.21% and Algae 0.77% and 0.11% by occurrence and volumetric respectively. This would be the first study conducted on the gut analysis of *Rita rita* from Local fish Market. The current study concluded that the fish is omnivorous.

Keywords: Rita, Fish, Gastronomic, Gut Analysis, Bagridae, Balochistan

Introduction

Fish generally arrive from Jaffarabad, Sukkar, and Karachi to Quetta. Most of them-about 80%-come from the Indus River, while others are farm fish. Fishermen claim that freshwater fish are more in demand than sea fish in the fish market in Quetta City. Because they have an excellent flavor and are available in close proximity to Quetta's fish market. Fish are available all year long at this market, but from August to March, individuals tend to consume the most seafood. Fish is one of the healthiest and most nutrient-dense sources of animal protein known to man. It is also one of the cheapest. Thus, there has been a noticeable growth in the consumption of fish in recent years. The exploitation of

Pakistani fisheries is currently transitioning from traditional to contemporary methods. Fisheries are considered renewable resources and are important to the nation's economy. In order to improve fisheries and meet global demand for fish, scientific research to advance cultural practices is now essential.

It has been stated that Pakistan and Kashmir are home to 180 native freshwater fish species, including 37 species of catfish from the order siluriformes. Food fish known as *Rita, rita* is sold in Afghanistan, Pakistan, India, Nepal, Bangladesh, and Burma (Mirza, 2003). It is a bottom-dwelling carnivorous catfish that eats insects, crustaceans, tiny fish, mollusks, and other organic debris that has begun to decompose (Shrestha, 1990).

The types of food available, the season, the time of day, the location in which they are located, and the size, age, sex, life history stage, have all been documented to affect a fish's diet and eating patterns (Lagler, *et al.*, 2003). When feeding is restricted or stopped, catfish develop more slowly. Since muscle growth is slowed down, a temporary feed limitation may have an adverse effect on the fish's processing yield. The need for energy for maintenance can be satisfied by a muscle. In late fall through early spring, when cold water temperatures inhibit feed intake and feeding is curtailed, processing yield often decreases in catfish (Bosworth *et al.*, 2002). In a pond, catfish feeding activity was found to be regulated by the feed ingested the day before rather than by daily water temperature, dissolved oxygen, and other environmental factors throughout the growth season (Taylor *et al.*, 1999). Several fish species have been the only ones whose feed consumption has been substantially measured (Silverstein and Shimma, 1994; Bellardi *et al.*, 1995). The goal of the current study was to monitor the eating behaviors of a wild population of catfish, *R. rita* from Quetta city's fish market in Balochistan, Pakistan.

Materials and Methods:

Sampling area

The local fish market in Quetta, Pakistan, was where fresh *Rita* samples were procured.

Collection of fish samples

260 *Rita* specimens were purchased at the Quetta neighborhood fish market between January 2022 and December 2022. In plastic bags containing water and oxygen, live experimental fish were sent to the Quetta lab department of the Balochistan University of Zoology.

Analysis of Gut contents

Each fish was carefully cut open, the stomach was removed, and it was then submerged in formalin solution containing 5–10% of the weight of the fish. With a Nikon Eclipse E200 binocular

microscope, the stomach contents were thoroughly examined and the following keys were used to identify them: Sangpradub and Boonsoong (2006); Wards and Whipple (1959); Pennak (1989).

Estimation of gut contents

In order to evaluate the stomach contents, Hynes' frequency of occurrence approach and Pillay's point volumetric method were both used (1950). The volume of each food item in the intestine determines how many points it receives in the point volumetric approach (Zacharia & Abdurahiman, 2004).

$$\text{Point volumetric method} = \frac{\text{No of points allocated to component}}{\text{Total points allocated to sub - sample}} \times 100$$

Each meal item is recognized and preserved following the investigation of gastrointestinal contents. According to Zacharia and Abdurahiman (2004), frequency of occurrence is the measurement of the proportion of stomachs in which each dietary item is present. Hynes' formula is used to demonstrate this concept: (1950).

$$P = \frac{b}{a} \times 100$$

a = Total No of fish examined with food in gut

b = No of fish containing particular food item

P = Percentage of occurrence of each food item

Gastro -somatic index (GaSI)

The gastro-somatic index GaSI was determined to examine monthly differences in feeding intensity using the equation (Dadzie *et al.*, 2000; Biswas, 1993, as cited in Achakzai, Saddozai, & Baloch, 2015).

$$\text{GaSI (\%)} = \frac{\text{Weight of gut (g)}}{\text{Weight of fish (g)}} \times 100$$

Gut fullness and its Categories

A gravimetric approach was used to measure the fullness of the gut (Hynes, 1950).

$$\text{Gravimetric method} = \frac{\text{Total gut contents weight}}{\text{Total fish weight}} \times 100$$

According to the amount of food in their guts, the test fish were divided into five groups: empty (0%), quarter (25%), half (50%), three-quarters (75%) and full (100%).

Index of preponderance

The amount and frequency of various dietary products are summarized by the index of predominance. It offers a distinct and quantifiable basis for the categorization of various food products (Zacharia & Abdurahiman, 2004). Using the method provided by Natarajan and Jhingran, the index of predominance is derived (1961).

$$I = \frac{V_i O_i}{\sum V_i O_i} \times 100 \text{ Where}$$

I = Index of preponderance

V_i = Volume percentage

O_i = Occurrence percentage

∑ = Summation

Results:

The gastrointestinal analysis of over 260 fish samples was determined by dissection. Fish meat and phytoplankton made up the majority of the stomach contents. The frequency of occurrence and point volumetric methods were used to determine the food's composition. The following is a paraphrase from the Rita were recorded (Table. 1 & Figure. 1, 3).

1. Gut Contents:

a) Fishes: Undigested, Digested and semi-digested fishes were the most dominant food item found the guts. They were 25.22% and 26.31% by volumetric and occurrence method.

b) Phytoplankton: Various types of phytoplankton were found in the guts. This was the second highest food item. They were 14.21% and 12.22% respectively.

c) Zooplankton: The third most common food item was zooplankton. They were 11.10% and 13.50% respectively.

d) Crustacean: Different types of crustaceans were recorded during the study period. They were 9.33% and 11.26% respectively.

e) Insects: Various types of insect legs and wings were noticed during the study period. They were 8.41% and 10.29% respectively.

f) Plecoptera: They were 6.88% and 8.11% by volumetric and occurrence method.

g) Hemiptera: Different species were recorded. They were 7.12% and 6.22% respectively.

h) Coleoptera: They were 5.24% and 5.22% respectively.

i) Mud and Sand: In most of the stomach very less amount of the mud and sand were recorded. They were 5.33 %and 4.19% respectively.

J) Miscellaneous: The unidentified food items were 2.99% and 1.24% by volumetric and occurrence method.

k) Leaves: They were 2.38% and 1.12% respectively.

l) Aquatic weeds: They were 1.02% and 0.21% respectively.

m) Algae: They were 0.77% and 0.11% by occurrence and volumetric respectively.

The gut fullness and Gastrosomic index were also calculated (Table. 2 & Figure. 2).The seasonal variations were noted by all the guts. There were around of 41 (14.28%) stomachs were empty, 63 (23.21%) were three quarter, 46 (16.07%) were full, and half guts were 62 (28.59%). The gut fullness on a monthly basis in month of January 80%, February (75%), March (72%), April (70%), June (60%), July (65%), August (70%), September (79%), October (87%), November (88%) and December (85%) respectively. The months of October and December saw the greatest rates of gastrostomia, while June saw the lowest rates. (Table. 3 & Figure. 3).

Table: 1 grading of various food items of gut contents in *Rita rita* from Local fish Market Quetta

S.no	Food items	% composition of items by		ViOi	Index of preponderance	Grade by Volume
		Volume (Vi)	Occurrence (Oi)			
					$I = \frac{ViOi}{\sum ViOi} \times 100$	
1	Fishes	25.22	26.31	663.5382	41.48	I
2	Phytoplankton	14.21	12.22	173.6462	20.71	II
3	Zooplankton	11.1	13.5	149.85	13.45	III
4	Crustacean	9.33	11.26	105.0558	8.34	IV
5	Insects	8.41	10.29	86.5389	6.05	V
6	Plecoptera	6.88	8.11	55.7968	3.74	VI
7	Hemiptera	7.12	6.22	44.2864	2.23	VII
8	Coleoptera	5.24	5.22	27.3528	1.5	VIII
9	Mud and Sand	5.33	4.19	22.3327	1.05	IX
10	Miscellaneous	2.99	1.24	3.7076	0.67	X
11	Leaves	2.38	1.12	2.6656	0.5	XI
12	Aquatic weeds	1.02	0.21	0.2142	0.25	XII
13	Algae	0.77	0.11	0.0847	0.03	XIII
			$\sum ViOi = 1335.0699$			

FOOD ITEMS OF *R.rita* BY VOLUME AND OCCURANCE

Figure 1: Food items of *R.rita*

Table 2. GaSI (gastrostomatic index) and monthly gut fullness of *R. rita* local fish market, Quetta City

Months	Gut fullness	GaSI
January	80	1.6
February	75	1.5
March	72	1.4
April	70	1.3
May	68	1.3
June	60	1.2
July	65	1.3
August	70	1.1
September	79	1.6
October	87	1.7
November	88	1.8
December	85	1.7
Average	78.75	1.46

Figure 2: Gut fullness of *R.rita*

Figure 3: Index Of preponderance of *R.ita*

Table 3. Stomach of *R. rita* from Local fish Market of Quetta City.

State	No of guts	Percentage
Empty	41	14.28
Quarter	48	17.85

Half	62	28.59
Three Quarter	63	23.21
Full	46	16.07
	260	100

Figure 4: No of guts of *R.rita*

Discussion

In this study, *Rita rita* food and feeding preferences were shown for different seasons, and feeding intensity was varied among fish size groups in *R. rita* at both the seasonal and ontogenic scales. There is evidence that fish species' eating habits are influenced by environmental food availability. In its early life, the fish likewise had a typical character, which changed as it grew larger and adopted an omnivorous eating style. Fish scales, teleost, mollusks, and plant materials were also common food sources in the bigger size groups, while crustaceans made up the majority of the diet in the lower size groups. A significant argument for the current study is (Noor et al. 2013). They claimed that *R. rita* is a carnivorous fish, with insects, crustaceans, and small fish constituting the majority of its diet. Fish maturity and the state of the feed were both connected. Fish that were adults ate a variety of things. According to recent fish growth patterns, many fish alter their diet as they become older, a discovery that Frost (1945) also recorded. By stating that insects, crustaceans, and protozoans made up the majority of intestinal contents, Bhuiyan (1964) came to the same conclusion as us. This research also included zooplankton (mainly copepods and cladocerans). The reported copepods and cladocerans from the same fish by Begum et al. (2008) lends additional weight to these conclusions. The current research on *R. rita*'s eating behavior may help advance understanding of the sustainable management of this possibly overfished and endangered fish species. Also, the

findings of this research may help in the development of effective feed formulation methods for this species' aquaculture.

REFERENCES

- Bella Dabre . Ink, W.I. and Fink, s.v., 1979. *Biochem. Physiol.*, 62(A): 13–29. Checklist of Freshwater fishes of Pakistan. *Pakistan. J. Zool. Suppl.* 3: 1-30.
- Habits of some catfishes of Punjab, Pakistan. *Pakistan. J. Zool.*, 35(1): 74-78. *Hist.Soc.*, 37: 657-662.
- HTNew and Noteworthy Venezuelan Glanapterygine Catfishes (Siluriformes, Trichomycteridae), with Discussion of Their Biogeography and PsammophilyTH. *American Museum Novitates*, 3496: 1-27.
- Ichthyol. Explor. Freshwater*, 4: 309-342.
- Ichthyology*. 2nd Ed, John Wiley and Sons. New York. pp506.
- ISLAM, A., 1951. The comparative history of the alimentary canal of certain freshwater.
- KHAN, H., 1934. Habits and habitats of food fishes of the Punjab, *J. Bombay Nat.*
- LAGLER, K. F., BARDCH, J.E., MILLER, R. R. AND PASSINO, D.R.M., 2003. Manaus, Brazil. NELSON, J.S., 2006. *Fishes of the World*. John Wiley and Sons, Inc.
- MIRZA, M.R. AND SHARIF, H.M., 1996. A key to the fishes of Punjab. *Polymer*
- NELSON, J.A., 1999. Comparisn of metabolism in two species of Panapue (Loricariidae). In: *Biology of Tropical Fishes* (eds. A.L, Val and V.M. Almedia INPA, Publication, Lahore. pp 1-32 MIRZA, M.R., 2003.
- SANDHU, I.A. AND LONE, K.P., 2003. Seasonal variation in the food and feeding
- SANDHU, I.A., 2000. *Comparative Anatomical and Histological Studies of the Gastrointestinal Tract of Some Freshwater Catfishes in Relation to their Food (Pisces:*
- SCHAEFER, S. A AND STEWARD, D.J., 1993. Systematic of Panaque dentex species group (Siliurformes: Loricariidae)wood eating armo from tropical south America.
- SHRESTHA, T.K., 1990. Rare fishes of Himalayan Waters of Nepal. *J. Fish Biol.* 37 (Supplement A): 213- 216.
- SILVERSTEIN, J.T. AND SHIMMA, H. 1994. Effectof restricted feeding on early maturation in female and male amago salmon, *Oncorhyncus masou* Ishikawae. *J.Fish Biol.* 45: 133-135.

- Siluriformes). Ph.,D Thesis. Department of Zoology University of the Punjab, Lahore. Pp 278.
- TAYLOR, J.B., HARGREAVES, J., TUCKER, C AND KINGSBURY, S. 1999. Influence on daily fluctuation in feeding activity of pond raised channel catfish. Abstract. Aquaculture America 1999. Tempa, EL. teleost fishes. Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci., 33(B): 297-321.
- Tschaefer, S.A., Provenzano, F.D., Pinna, M. and Baskin, J.N., 2005. U.K. pp. 350.

